

Review

Recurrent Papillomatosis of the Larynx. Etiological Aspects, Risk Factors and the Prognosis of Clinical Evolution: A Review of Literature

Daniela Cernev, PhD and Vasile Cabac, Md. PhD

Abstract

Conferențiar universitar, Universitatea de Stat de Medicină, și Farmacie "Nicolae Testemițanu"

Email: vasile.cabac@usmf.md

Recurrent laryngeal papillomatosis is a benign condition caused by human papillomavirus (HPV), which is characterized by recurrent proliferation of papillomas in the respiratory tract and can occur in both children and adults. There is currently no curable treatment for PLR. Only surgical procedures are needed to improve voice quality and prevent respiratory obstruction. The aim of the study is to evaluate the etiological aspects, risk factors and prognosis of the clinical evolution of recurrent laryngeal papillomatosis according to the literature review. Review was done on data base-based on literature: Embase, MedLine, and Evidence-Based Medicine Reviews, using various keyword combinations related to the etiology of laryngeal papillomatosis, risk factors, and disease severity. Seven long-term studies were analyzed, which showed that RLP occurs more frequently in patients with pathological laryngopharyngeal reflux that was diagnosed in 8/20 (40.0%) adults and 5/11 children (45.5%). Moreover, logistic regression revealed that only age at onset was associated with aggressive disease in young people, while HPV-11 and observation time > 10 years were risk factors in adults. RLP associated with HPV-11 behaves more aggressively: younger patients with HPV-11 and older with HPV-6 develop more severe clinical evolution. Laryngopharyngeal reflux may be a risk factor in the development of laryngeal papillomatosis, by activating or reactivating a latent HPV infection.

Keywords. HPV, Recurrent laryngeal papillomatosis, Risk factors

INTRODUCTION

Recurrent papillomatosis of the larynx is a relatively rare, benign pathology. It is caused by HPV infection and is characterized by the development of exophyte proliferative lesions of the connective tissue covered by the epithelium, which affects the lining of the upper respiratory tract. It is called laryngeal papillomatosis or glottal papillomatosis due to the intense predilection for the larynx, but papillomas can occur anywhere along the respiratory tract (Reeves et al., 2003; Gélinas et al., 2008). The disease is classified as juvenile onset, if it develops until the age of 18, and onset in adults for cases that develop after the age of 18 (Derkay, 1995; Wiatrak et al., 2004). Most infections in children occur at birth. In

adults, viral transmission occurs during oral sex. Reactivation of a latent HPV infection acquired in childhood is another possible cause (Derkay CS, 1995). Papillomas usually appear as exophyte nodes, mostly in the larynx, but may occasionally involve the nasopharynx, tracheobronchial tree, and lung parenchyma. The clinical course of the disease is unpredictable - from spontaneous remission to persistent or recurrent aggressive disease. Although rare, recurrent laryngeal papillomatosis has the potential to turn into squamous cell carcinoma (Fusconi et al., 2014; Carifi et al., 2015).

HPV subtypes are classified as high and low risk, depending on their potential for malignant transformation

of epithelial cells (Farrel et al., 2019; Chesson et al., 2008). Subtypes 6 and 11 are responsible for more than 90% of cases of recurrent laryngeal papillomatosis (Robin et al., 2015; Fusconi et al., 2014). Patients infected with HPV type 11 develop a more aggressive disease (Chesson et al., 2008), which can lead to significant airway obstruction. They require frequent surgical procedures and adjuvant medical therapies, and sometimes even tracheostomy, to maintain the patent of the respiratory tract (Robin et al., 2015). Other subtypes, such as 16, 18, 31, and 33, are also associated with PLR, although they have a lower incidence (Reeves et al., 2003; Gélinas et al., 2008). Subtypes 16 and 18 have a high risk, with the potential for malignant transformation, especially in squamous cell carcinoma, which occurs in less than 1% of cases of juvenile PLR (Derkay, 1995; Fusconi et al., 2014; Katsenos and Becker, 2011).

In the last two decades, the incidence has remained relatively consistent worldwide at less than 0.01%, with minor variability between adult and young subpopulations (Derkay, 1995; Larson and Derkay, 2010; Derkay CS, 1995). PLR is usually caused by low-risk human papillomavirus (HPV) types 6 and 11 (Duggan et al., 1990). The clinical course of laryngeal papillomatosis is different: in some patients they experience spontaneous remission for a period of time, and in others they show an aggressive recurrent increase (Gélinas et al., 2008). To date, there is no cure for the disease, but treatment aims to control symptoms and reduce the intensity of the disease (Ruiz et al. 2014). The current standard in the treatment of recurrent laryngeal papillomatosis are surgical excision, primarily with microdebridors and lasers, and adjuvant therapies (if necessary) (Chesson et al., 2008).

There is currently no cure for recurrent laryngeal papillomatosis. Only surgical procedures are needed to improve voice quality and prevent respiratory obstruction. The evolution of the disease is high, it frequently recurs, it can be even throughout life and hospitalizations are often necessary. Clinical complications may occur as a result of frequent surgical procedures, papillomatous involvement of the lower respiratory tract, and therapeutic resistance.

A study conducted in 2017 in the US by the National Center for Health Statistics (NCHS) for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) examined the incidence of oral HPV infection in more than 9,000 participants aged 18 to 69 years. 7% of the studied population has detectable HPV DNA in the oral cavity. When separated by genotype, about 1% of the population has an oral cavity infected with HPV-6 or HPV-11, but only a small proportion of those infected develop recurrent laryngeal papillomatosis. Current hypotheses suggest that several genes predispose individuals to tolerate HPV 6/11 infection. Genetic analyzes of patients with laryngeal papillomatosis have revealed an increased frequency of certain alleles of human leukocyte antigen (HLA) as well

as a decrease in the frequency of certain receptors. Immune cells, which can predispose individuals to the development of the given pathology and can be correlated with the severity of the disease. When HPV infects the epithelium of susceptible individuals, HPV oncoproteins, especially E6, can interfere with innate immunity and swallow the adaptive immune response to similar type 2 (Th2) T cells or T (Treg) regulation. This inclined adaptive immune response, in combination with a modified innate immune response, produces an HPV-tolerant cytokine microenvironment (Ivancic et al., 2020).

Objective of the study

Evaluation of the etiological aspects, risk factors and prognosis of the clinical evolution of recurrent laryngeal papillomatosis according to the literature review.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The paper presents a review of the recent literature. The study is based on the available literature sources related to the studied problem: *Recurrent laryngeal papillomatosis. Etiological aspects, risk factors and prognosis of clinical evolution*. We reviewed the literature based on EMBASE, MEDLINE, and Evidence-Based Medicine Reviews (EBMR), using various keyword combinations related to the etiology of laryngeal papillomatosis, risk factors, and disease severity. The selection was also based on Google Scholar and reference lists of eligible studies.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Most previous studies have concluded that HPV-11 is associated with a more aggressive clinical course than HPV-6. Although clinicians question whether knowledge of the HPV type can predict the clinical course, this concept has been challenged by some authors, who have shown that age of onset is a better indicator of the clinical course than the HPV type (Buchinsky et al., 2008; Cuello et al., 2013; Omland et al., 2014). Other risk factors remain controversial. Macroscopic enlargement of recurrent laryngeal papillomatosis lesions during the first endoscopy, before treatment, could be one of these prognostic factors. It is known that the link between the initial spread and the severity of the disease has never really been explored. Multiple therapeutic techniques, which were not consented to until the 1998 clinical and laryngoscopic evaluation scale of Derkay, are now being applied by otorhinolaryngologists who are concerned with recurrent laryngeal papillomatosis (Derkay et al., 1998).

Farrel et al. (2019) conducted a study to determine the scientific truth of the factors that cause recurrent

laryngeal papillomatosis, its evolution and complications. This cohort study included 339 patients with laryngeal papillomatosis, who were monitored for more than 1 year. The results of the examination showed: 82% were diagnosed by the age of 18, 65% were infected with HPV-6, and 69% had an aggressive clinical course. When we compare the age at diagnosis with the clinical evolution, the probability of aggression is high in children under five, then decreases rapidly. For patients diagnosed after the age of 10, aggression is more common.

Robin et al. (2015) aimed to compare the clinical outcome, aggressiveness and response to treatment between HPV-6 and HPV-11. 55 patients were observed (1974-2012): 76% of them (42 out of 55) were infected with HPV-6 and 24% (13 out of 55) were infected with HPV-11. The HPV-11 group had a more common anatomical disease. The expected number of surgeries was higher in patients with HPV-11 in the younger age group (<22.4 years) and in the group with HPV-6 (> 22.4 years). Regardless of the type of HPV, the early age of onset of laryngeal papillomatosis required a greater number of surgeries. Therefore, younger patients with HPV-11 and older patients with HPV-6 are experiencing a more severe clinical course of recurrent laryngeal papillomatosis.

Garcia-Romero and coauthor.[24] aimed to identify the human papillomavirus (HPV) isotype in 35 adult men with recurrent respiratory papillomatosis, which may be important in defining the precise etiology of the disease and in applying therapeutic and prophylactic measures. The men were treated for several years and included in the study. Patients' DNA was extracted from fresh biological samples and analyzed by PCR and a Linear Array ® HPV genotyping system. Most cases (95%) corresponded to the onset in adults. A questionnaire was applied to obtain demographic and clinical data. Using a PCR-based detection system, the presence of HPV was demonstrated in all patients; 80% were positive for HPV-6, 8% for HPV-11 and one for HPV-16. Most patients had HPV-6 and therefore it was not possible to correlate clinical and demographic characteristics with the viral type. In addition, the co-infections were not obvious. This knowledge may be relevant for the delimitation of therapeutic and preventive measures.

Although the prevalence of HPV is high, the incidence of papillomatosis is low. Probably, factors other than HPV infection favor the development of laryngeal papillomatosis. M. Formanek and coauthor.[25] examined whether patients with papillomatosis are more frequently infected with Herpes simplex virus type 2 and Chlamydia trachomatis and whether laryngopharyngeal reflux (LFR) occurs more frequently in this group of patients. The study included 20 adult patients with LFR and 20 adult patients with CV cyst and no laryngeal mucosal pathology. Thus, pathological RLF was diagnosed in 8/20 (40.0%) patients with laryngeal papillomatosis and in

control patients 0/20 ($P = 0.03$). Herpes simplex virus type 2 was present in 9/20 (45.0%) patients with laryngeal papillomatosis and in control patients 0/20 ($P = 0.001$). Five specimens were positive for both laryngopharyngeal reflux and Herpes simplex virus type 2. No samples were positive for Chlamydia trachomatis. There were no significant differences between age groups, body mass index, diabetes and gastroesophageal reflux disease. Exposure to tobacco was not more common in the PLR group ($P = 0.01$). Thus, the results show that LFR and Herpes simplex virus type 2 are significantly more common in patients with recurrent laryngeal papillomatosis. LFR and Herpes simplex virus type 2 may activate latent HPV infection and therefore may be risk factors for the development of laryngeal papillomatosis.

Turid et al. (2014) examined whether gender, age at onset, time of observation, and human papillomavirus (HPV) genotype are risk factors for an aggressive clinical course in recurrent laryngeal papillomatosis. Clinical data from patient records included sex, age at onset, date of first endolaryngeal biopsy procedure, date of last monitoring, total number of endolaryngeal procedures, and complications during the observation period. DNA was extracted from tissue incorporated into formalin. HPV genotyping was performed by quantitative PCR analysis with the identification of 15 HPV genotypes. The study included 224 patients. The majority were men (141/174 adults and 31/50 children; $P = 0.005$). After diagnosis, the monitoring period was 12 years (IQR 3.7-32.9) for children and 4.0 years (IQR 0.8-11.7) for adults. The disease was more aggressive in young people than in adults ($P < 0.001$); the difference disappeared after 10 years of observation. HPV-6 or 11 was present in all HPV-positive papillomas. HPV-11 was more prevalent in aggressive diseases, and HPV-6 in non-aggressive diseases ($P < 0.001$). Multiple logistic regression revealed that only age at onset was associated with aggressive disease in young people, while HPV-11 and observation time > 10 years were risk factors in adults.

Ilboudo et al. (2019) aimed to describe the involvement of HPV-6 and HPV-11 in cases of histologically confirmed laryngeal papillomatosis in Burkina Faso. This study was based on histologically diagnosed archival tissue, obtained in the last ten years (2007 - 2017) in anatomy and cytopathology laboratories. The prevalence of low-risk HPV infection (HPV-LR) was 54.84% in histologically confirmed laryngeal papillomatosis. In the HPV-LR positive samples, the HPV-6 and HPV-11 genotypes prevailed, respectively 41.17% and 35.3%, while the HPV-6 / HPV-11 coinfection was 23.53%.

Abramson et al. (1987) reviewed the clinical course and pathology of 57 patients with laryngeal papillomatosis. Tissues from 26 patients were analyzed for human papillomavirus (HPV) DNA by Southern blot hybridization. Histopathological evaluation of papillomas

did not show any correlation with the age of onset or with the clinical pattern of remission and recurrence. The pathology was characterized by abnormal squamous maturation with parakeratosis, delayed superficial cell maturation, papillomatosis and basal hyperplasia. HPV DNA was present in all lesions, and 92% of them contained either HPV-6 or HPV-11. Latent HPV DNA was detected in clinically undeveloped tissues in 11 of 14 (78.5%) patients studied. There was no correlation between HPV type, histopathology and clinical pattern. Despite the homogeneity of the pathology, the clinical expression of laryngeal HPV infection varied greatly.

Silverberg et al. (2003) assessed the risk of occurring laryngeal papillomatosis, as conferred by the maternal history of genital warts in pregnancy and the identification of additional cofactors, such as the method of birth (cesarean versus vaginal) and complications during pregnancy. Using data from Danish registries, the authors identified 3033 births with maternal history of genital warts during pregnancy. Fifty-seven cases of respiratory papillomatosis were identified by reviewing medical documents in the ENT departments. Seven out of every 1,000 births with a maternal history of genital warts resulted in a disease in offspring, which corresponds to a 231.4 (95% confidence interval 135.3; 395.9) times higher risk of the disease. In relation to births without maternal history of genital warts. In women with genital warts, birth rates of more than 10 hours have been associated with twice the risk of disease. Cesarean delivery has not been shown to be protective against respiratory papillomatosis and no other procedures or complications have been observed during pregnancy that increase the risk of the disease.

Moreddu et al. (2019) aimed to determine the risk factors for the severity of recurrent laryngeal papillomatosis with juvenile onset at the first endoscopic evaluation. Based on a review of all cases undergoing surgery for the given pathology, the following severe risk factors were analyzed in two pediatric otorhinolaryngology departments in the US and France: the number of laryngeal levels involved, subglottic extension and bilateral involvement. Thirty-two patients were included, with 571 endoscopic procedures. The number of endoscopies per patient varied depending on the initial extension: 30.67 procedures - involving three levels, 15.57 procedures - involving two levels and 14.08 procedures - involving only one level ($P = 0, 03$). The risk ratio for > 14 procedures involving 3 levels was 20.43 ($P = 0.047$). The initial subglottic extension was associated with several endoscopic procedures (23.67 versus 15.56, $P = 0.16$).

Draganov et al. (2006) evaluated the occurrence of HPV types in a group of patients with juvenile laryngeal papillomatosis. The study included 23 patients. Laryngeal biopsies were taken and investigated for the presence of HPV DNA, using real-time polymerase chain reaction (PCR) with a set of consensus polymers (MY09 / 11).

Viral testing was subsequently performed by real-time PCR with polymers specific to HPV types 6, 11, 16, 18, 31 and 33. HPV-11 was detected in 61.9% of patients and HPV-6 in 23.8%. Double positivity for HPV-6 and HPV-11 types was identified in 14.3% of cases. The results suggest that laryngeal papillomatosis develops a more aggressive clinical course when HPV-11 infection is present ($p = 0.0265$).

Cuello et al. (2013) described the factors associated with aggressive forms of recurrent laryngeal papillomatosis. 189 cases diagnosed in 1985-2009 were identified in the pathological registries. 113 patients had a single surgery (less aggressive) and 76 patients two or more interventions (more aggressive). The likelihood of developing aggressive lesions decreased with increasing age at diagnosis and HPV-11 was not associated with a significant increase in the risk of aggression.

Martin et al. (2019) investigated laryngopharyngeal reflux - if possible, a risk factor for the development of juvenile laryngeal papillomatosis. The study covered the period November 2015 - November 2017. Using the immunohistochemical method, HPV infection associated with RLF were diagnosed from laryngeal biopsies. 11 children (aged between 4 and 14 years) were analyzed. No patient had a history of immunodeficiency or exposure to tobacco smoke. All patients underwent at least three surgeries due to papillomatosis and were vaccinated against HPV. Five children were treated with antivirals and immunomodulators. All 11 samples were infected with HPV (type 6 or 11). Pathological RLF was diagnosed in 5/11 children (45.5%).

CONCLUSIONS

1. Recurrent laryngeal papillomatosis associated with HPV-11 behaves more aggressively. Younger patients with HPV-11 and older patients with HPV-6 develop more severe clinical progression.
2. The initial spread of papillomatous lesions to multiple or subglottic laryngeal levels has been shown to be a severe risk factor with more endoscopes.
3. Age at diagnosis is the main determinant of the aggressiveness of recurrent laryngeal papillomatosis.
4. Laryngopharyngeal reflux may be a risk factor in the development of juvenile laryngeal papillomatosis, by activating or reactivating a latent HPV infection.

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